

The Chemical Examination of the Oil from the Seeds *Butea Frondosa*, Roxb.

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The seeds of *Butea Frondosa* are used in Ayurvedic medicine as an anthelmintic drug. (Nadkarni, "The Indian Materia Medica," 1927, p. 135). Since very little work has been done on the fixed oil in them, the following investigation was undertaken. The observations of Weber and Heckel that the oil formed 18% of the seeds (Wehmer, "Die Pflanzenstoffe," pp. 366, 804) were confirmed. As it was not possible to press out the oil even after steaming the crushed seeds, it was extracted by means of light petroleum (b.p. 50-80°).

TABLE I.

Physical and Chemical Constants of the Oil.

Specific gravity	... 0.8988 at 25°/25°
Refractive index	... 1.4650 at 25°
Solidifying point	... 15°
Saponification value	... 178
Iodine value (Hanus)	... 67.2
Acetyl ,,	... 23.6
Acid ,,	... 18.1
Reichert-Meisel value	... 0.5
Hehner ,,	... 88.6
Unsaponifiable matter	... 2.3%

Total fatty acids.

Mean molecular weight	... 308.7
Iodine value (Hanus)	... 64.6
Saturated acids (Twitchell's method)	... 35.9%
Unsaturated acids (,,)	... 64.3%

The oil was saponified by alcoholic potash and the resulting soap was dried on paper-pulp and extracted with ether to separate unsaponifiable matter. The soap was then dissolved in water and the fatty acids liberated by the addition of excess of mineral acid. The separation of saturated and unsaturated acids was effected by Twitchell's method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, **13**, 806). The unsaturated acids were converted into their methyl esters which were fractionally distilled under reduced pressure.

TABLE II.

(177 gm. of the esters were distilled.)

Fraction.	Pressure in mm.	Range of temperature.	Distillate in g.	Mean mol. wt. of acids from saponification value.	Iodine value.
I	1.5	Up to 155°	1.47
II	..	155-168°	45.87	276.3	115.5
III	0.7	152-153°	22.06	274.5	115.7
IV	0.5	153-154°	21.76	275.6	115.4
V	1.2	154-156°	37.62	282.0	121.1
VI	..	156-160°	18.90	282.7	118.5
VII	1.5	160-170°	4.76	265.8	106.0
VIII	..	170-190°	3.51	258.6	89.0
IX	..	192-206°	4.46	246.0	78.7

The higher fractions showed that with the decreased molecular weights of the acids, the iodine values also decreased considerably. They probably consisted of decomposition products and were rejected. The acids were liberated from the lower fractions. A portion of the mixed acids was treated with bromine according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler (*Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes,"* 6th edition, Vol. I, 585). No ether insoluble additive compound was formed, indicating the absence of linolic acid. Among the products obtained was isolated tetrabromostearic acid (m.p. 113-114°), which pointed to the presence of linolic acid. On oxidising the acids by cold alkaline permanganate solution, dihydroxystearic acid (m.p. 128-130.5°, mol. wt. 315) and tetrahydroxystearic

acid (m.p. 145-162°*, mol. wt. 349) were formed. The former established the presence of oleic acid and the latter confirmed that of linolic acid.

The saturated acids proved to be of far greater interest. The acids on separation (iodine value, 1.2) were converted into their methyl esters which were subjected to fractional distillation under diminished pressure.

TABLE III.

(243 g. of the esters were distilled.)

Fraction.	Pressure in mm.	Range of temperature.	Distillate in g.	Mean mol. wt. of acids from saponification value.	Acids isolated.
I	2.5	Up to 160°	1.6	281.1	A
II	1.5	160-161°	61.0	270.6	A
III	..	161-165°	24.8	269.3	A
IV	..	165-172°	28.0	273.0	A, C and D
V	2.5	185-190°**	20.7	291.0	A, B and C
VI	..	190-197°	24.0	308.3	B and C
VII	2.0	197-205°	25.2	331.4	B, C and D
VIII	..	205-212°	36.7	343.9	D
IX	..	212-222°	19.3	355.4	D and E
X	Residue		1.5	373.0	F

Acid fractions.	M.p.	Mean mol. wt.
A	55-56°	270
B	61-62°	303 (9 g.)
C	75-76°	344 (8 g.)
D	74.5-75.5°	353 (30 g.)
E	77-79°	368 (8 g.)
F	77.5-79°	383 (1 g.)

* It is interesting to note that the tetrahydroxystearic acid obtained melted over a wide range. On melting, the substance solidified at 144° and remelted sharply at 162°. Repeated recrystallisations from various solvents including water did not alter this characteristic of the acid, which is probably a mixture of several isomers.

** 3.4 C.c. of the distillate were collected between 172° and 185°.

The acid from the lower fractions (A) melted at 55-56° (mol. wt. 270). Owing to the fact that successive recrystallisations from various solvents did not alter either its m. p. or M. W. it appeared to be an isomer of margaric acid (m.p. 59.5°, Krafft, *Ber.*, 1879, **12**, 1673). In order to establish its homogeneity fractional precipitation of the magnesium salt (Heintz, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1855, *i* **66**, 3) was also tried but no separation was effected. However, quite fortuitously, during one of the crystallisations from alcohol a small amount of material separated out melting at 57-58.5° (mol. wt. 266.4). The whole of the acid was converted into its methyl ester, which was then carefully fractionated under diminished pressure. The lower fractions thus obtained gave pure palmitic acid (m.p. 61-62.5°, mol. wt. 256.4). But it was not possible to obtain any information as to the nature of the higher acid present in the mixture. The acids from the higher ester fractions of (A) had indefinite melting points and their mol. wts. ranged from 290 to 324.

During this work no trace of stearic acid was obtained although the mol. wt. of acid fraction (A) corresponded to that of an equimolecular mixture of palmitic and stearic acids. In this connection it is interesting to note that Katti and Puntambaker (unpublished work), while working on the saturated acids from the oil contained in the seeds of *Caesalpinia bonducella*, obtained both palmitic and stearic acids, and another acid (m.p. 55-56°, mol. wt. 270) similar to the one under discussion from different fractions of the methyl esters of the total fatty acids. Their last acid was in all probability a mixture of the first two. In the present case, however, owing to the absence of any trace of stearic acid, it is to be deduced that the higher acid in the mixture is presumably one of the higher acids in the mixed fatty acids.

The next acid fraction isolated (B) had a constant melting point of 60-61° (mol. wt. 303). This was obviously a mixture and was proved to be such by the fractional distillation of its methyl ester. Although it was not possible to isolate any definite acid, the melting points and the mol. wts. of the acids * from the different fractions led to the above conclusion.

* Acids from fraction	...	I	II	III
M.p.		61-62°	62-63°	72.5-74°
Mol. wt.		300.9	315.4	346.2

There was obtained another acid fraction of a similar character (C) (m.p. 75-76°, mol. wt. 343), the methyl ester of which on fractional distillation was divided into two fractions. From the first was obtained an acid melting at 77-78° (mol. wt. 351.5). The second also gave an acid which had the same mol. wt., but the melting point was slightly lower (75-76°). No lower acid could be identified.

The acid fraction that proved very interesting was the one which had a constant melting point of 74.5-75.5° (mol. wt. 353). Holde, Bleyberg and Rabinowitsch (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 177) isolated a similar substance from the higher acids of the peanut oil (m.p. 73.5-75°, mol. wt. 354). The molecular weight corresponded to that of an equimolecular mixture of behenic and lignoceric acids. These latter acids also were isolated by them from the same source. Thus there is a strong possibility of their acid being a mixture. In the present case, however, although lignoceric acid was isolated from the IXth fraction of the esters, no indication of the occurrence of behenic acid was found. Consequently more detailed work was called for in order to establish the nature of this acid fraction (D).

As in other cases the methyl esters were prepared and fractionally distilled under reduced pressure.

TABLE IV.

(30 g. of the esters were taken. The pressure was less than one mm. throughout the distillation).

No. of fraction.	Range of temperature.	M.p. of acids isolated.	Mol. wt.
I	220-225°	i 77-78°	354.0
		ii ,,	345.6 (from mother-liquors of i)
II	225-227°	i 77-77.6°	352.0
		ii 77-78.3°	347.8 (from mother-liquors of i)
III	227-231°	i 75-76.5°	353.5
IV	Above 231°	i 75-76.5°	367.3 ("crude lignoceric acid")
		ii 75.5-77.2°	355.2 (from mother-liquors of i)

The results proved inconclusive. Higher melting acids (77-78°) were obtained from the first two ester fractions. The mother-liquors of these gave about a gram of substance melting at 77-78° (mol.

wt. 345.6). It may be recalled that the higher melting substance of mol. wt. 354 was also obtained from the acid fraction (C) The highest ester fraction, however, gave a small amount of "crude lignoceric acid" (m.p. 75-76.5°, mol. wt. 367.3).*

The results can be interpreted thus: The original acid was "crude tricosoic acid" and that the acid when pure melted at 77-78°. Levene and Taylor (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1924, 59, 921) synthesised *n*-tricosoic acid and found that it melted at 80-81°. The acid now described might be an isomer. The lower m.p. of the acid fraction (D) is due to the presence of small amounts of a lower acid and lignoceric acid. It is also possible that the acid is a mixture which cannot be definitely separated into its constituents by the process adopted.

In order to obtain more definite information, fractional precipitation of lithium salts (Holde and Godbole, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 36) was also attempted.

TABLE V.

No. of fraction.	M. p.	Mol. wt.
I	74-76°	353.6
II	74-75°	354.2
III	74-76°	353.8
IV	"	353.9

For this purpose the higher melting acid fraction (77-78°) was used. Four distinct fractions of the lithium salts were obtained. On liberating the acids from these, the m.p. was found to have been unaccountably lowered (74-76°) and the mol. wt. remained the same (354). This indicated that no separation had been effected. However, the results cannot be regarded as establishing the identity of the substance, since Holde and others (*loc. cit.*) were able to isolate a small amount of a higher acid from what appeared to be pentacosic

* Lignoceric acid obtained by Heiduschka and Pyoriki (*Pharm. Zentr.*, 1925, 66, 1) from the peanut oil melted at 77.5°, even after repeated crystallisations from alcohol. From such an acid Holde and Godbole (*loc. cit.*) were able to isolate pure lignoceric acid (m.p. 80-81°). Similarly Holde and others (*loc. cit.*) obtained *n*-behenic acid in a pure state (m.p. 79.2-80.1°) from "crude behenic acid" (m.p. 75.6-76.2°, mol. wt. 340). They consider that the depression of the melting point in these cases is due to the presence of a higher acid in quantities too small to be detected by molecular weight determinations.

acid according to this method. Distillation of the free acid in high vacuo (Holde and others, *loc. cit.*) is expected to lead to more definite conclusions.

From the IXth ester fraction lignoceric acid (m.p. 77-79°, mol. wt. 368) was isolated.

The residue in the distillation flask, on saponification and purification gave about a gram of an acid fraction (F) melting at 77.5-79° (mol. wt. 383). Holde and others (*loc. cit.*) obtained a similar acid (m.p. 78.3-78.8°) from the pea-nut oil; but as has already been mentioned, they isolated from this a small amount of material which approximated to hexacosic acid. Consequently that the present acid fraction represents a definite chemical entity seems questionable.

In this connection another interesting observation might be recorded. When a mixed melting point of acid fraction (F) with lignoceric acid was taken, no change was observed. This fact goes to indicate that in the case of the higher fatty acids the melting point by itself is not an accurate criterion of purity.

From the unsaponifiable matter a phytosterol (m.p. 133-134°) was isolated. The acetyl derivative of this substance melted at 125-126°. It was evidently sitosterol. The residue left after treatment with digitonin had an oily consistency and it was not possible to isolate any other definite compound.

Thus during this investigation the following compounds were isolated from the oil:

Among unsaturated acids	...	Oleic and linolic acids only.
„ saturated acids	...	Palmitic and lignoceric acids, and acids fractions of mol. wt. 354 and 383.
From unsaponifiable matter	...	Sitosterol.

A more detailed study of the higher acids will form the subject of another communication.

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